

One more step on a long road

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The Orthopaedic Journal of M P Chapter (OJMPC) is official publication of Madhya Pradesh Chapter of Indian Orthopaedic Association (IOA). This journal is academic representation of our esteemed body. Publishing a journal is not easy, it needs lot of determination, time and energy.

Till last year previous editors (Dr. P. K. Rai, Dr. HKT Raza, Dr. Sunil Rajan and Dr. Alok C Agrawal) have put all their efforts to improve the journal in terms of quantity and quality of scientific content. I must acknowledge Dr. Alok C Agrawal for two major breakthroughs in his long tenure of editorship one is getting ISSN and second indexing with Index Copernicus. As this is a free open access journal with no article submission or processing fee overcoming the financial hurdles was a big challenge for previous editors.

After the directives issued by Medical council of India to have publications in print journals with indexing in any of the following Pubmed, Index Medicus, Medline, Scopus and Index Copernicus etc the task became more difficult and technical. After this directive though the number of articles submitted are increasing but at the same time due to the pressing need lots of journals have cropped up thus compromising the

quality of the articles. In this scenario it is imperative to maintain ethical practice and publish high quality scientific material.

This is for the first time in history of Orthopaedic Journal of M P Chapter that journal is having its own website and this is the first online issue. From now onwards all manuscript submissions will be online and there will be a double blind peer review process. Journal will now have a National as well International readership.

As the journal will be assessed globally the number of submissions are going to be increased. Our mission is to have stringent peer review, high quality publications, improved indexing and improved impact factor. Very soon we will increase the number of issues published per year. However, being official publication of state chapter of IOA we expect more publications from our own members.

Publishing is a team work I thank all the members of editorial board, all the reviewers and technical team. We cordially invite you all to submit your manuscript in OJMPC, we assure you of good peer review and quick decision on articles. This is our own journal we must work together and contribute toward its growth.

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